

IMPACT OF GENDER FACTOR IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract

All the findings in this article conclude that the neurobiological basis for the development of such a complex communication system is weaker and that boys are more prone to disorders.

In this review, we have presented a number of studies in the field of neuroimaging that offer components that can help to address the gender gap mentioned.

Numerous studies have clearly shown a link between sex hormones and developmental outcomes. In addition, the anatomical, histological, and brain activation differences of the word and language brain have been documented.

Overall, the functioning of the female brain seems to give women a special advantage in acquiring more communication and language systems than men. The specific mechanisms that lead to and contribute to the development of this advantage have yet to be fully revealed.

Keywords: gender, language acquisition, language development, femininity, masculinity

Masculinity and femininity are represented in a number of different ways in our surrounding. The way people dress and how they do their hair convey how sex determines them according to the social structure or the male and female categories of a person. Gender is very dependent on how we describe ourselves, and may even affect the words we use in our everyday life.

Although sex may not seem to be related to language, unexpectedly it is. There are innumerable studies showing a strong link between gender and language acquisition, development, and its use. Gender seems to have an undeniable influence on the development of language, even from a variety of historical and cultural perspectives.

Gender may play an important role in sex education or in learning the mother tongue of young children. In many societies, infants and young children spend more time with female educators, so early language is often imitated by female speakers [1, 44].

In most language groups, young girls learn the language a little faster than boys, but this is the case in middle childhood. Gender differences in language use occur early; Girls are more likely to use language as part of emotional relationships with others, while boys use language to describe things and events.

On average, girls also learn to read a little earlier than boys, but this is the same as middle childhood. However, women perform slightly higher than average men in tests that measure speech acuity and productivity throughout their lives [2, 98].

There are some important differences in the development of language and how people express themselves on the basis of gender as well.

For example, women generally use the language more closely or in close contact with others. Women have a greater vocabulary, using language more easily to express their feelings and emotional states.

Men, on the other hand, use language more confidently and are more likely to suppress or retain their emotions. As a result, men do not express their feelings verbally. It should be noted that this is generalized and applies to all men and women in the world.

The way men and women use the language also varies according to the language in question. For example, some research states that female speakers of Chinese speak in a quieter and more passive voice than male speakers [4]. These differences have not been consistently documented in other languages.

Some kind of database was needed to explore the differences in college foreign language preferences of men and women. Initially, the idea was to collect data using master databases declared from universities in the United States.

But with this idea, more than one problem arose. In a few universities with up-to-date databases, there were many errors, such as defining a Spanish major and a Spanish Literature major in two different departments, both not in the foreign languages department.

Another inconsistency is that universities often have different requirements for what constitutes a major. For example, the same requirements for a Russian minor at Yale University are accepted as a Russian major at the University of New Hampshire. Additionally, some databases count students twice for different categories, meaning that a German major will also fall under a Germanic Languages major.

Because of this wide range of issues, it made more sense to rely on a comprehensive database rather than separate databases from different universities [4]. The website of the National Center for Education Statistics provided this comprehensive database.

From this website, which analyzes educational data from all schools in the United States, I was able to find a database of degrees awarded, put together by the Institute of Educational Sciences. This database consists of accredited universities and their degrees reported after graduation.

Among all the forms on Earth's face, humans have a unique ability to communicate using the symbolic communication system, that is, verbal and written language. This ability has contributed to the prosperity of mankind and has given more benefits than any other species.

The very complex language allowed people to establish a very precise and complex communication

within the tribe [5]. The complexity of the human language can be explained by a dictionary of about 42,000 words for an average 20-year-old child.

Such a complex system of communication is the backbone of our ever-changing public relations. The Social Brain Hypothesis emphasizes the importance of social connections for the development of the general phylogenetic brain, as well as for the development of multi-complex cognitive abilities that allow the use of symbolic communication systems.

This hypothesis suggests that the “cognitive demands of living in complex social groups” are the driving force behind the growth of the human brain and the development of complex functions. In addition, the hierarchy within social groups led to members of the group taking on different social roles.

Typically, female primates were engaged in raising children, collecting food, and building household utensils, while men were hunting. “Women’s work” is believed to have contributed to the functional evolution of speech spaces, and “men’s work” has contributed to men’s visual and spatial advantages.

Numerous studies have confirmed higher levels of speech in women [5]. The differences between men and women were confirmed not only for the study of the first language, but also for the acquisition of a foreign language.

Research in other primates suggests that gender differences in human communication and language skills may stem from differences between men and women in social tendencies that are “fundamentally rooted in our biological and evolutionary heritage”. For example, gender differences in social trends are documented in wild baby chimpanzees.

Likewise, newborn female articles look at faces more clearly than men, and in 4-5 weeks show more effective behaviors such as gestures, gestures, and intimacy with familiar and unfamiliar human educators.

Free-size rhetorical articles have highlighted gender-related differences in the level of production of social voices, reaffirming that women are more reliant on voice communication, which can play an important role in language evolutionary theories.

However, it is important to note that the differences in a person's verbal performance are not very subtle and are not consistently found in different linguistic issues, with varying results in different age groups.

It has long been known that boys and girls differ in the pace of language development. More than 60 years ago, McCarthy said, “These differences are statistically significant, but a careful observer cannot ignore the remarkable sequence of these small differences that are consistently analyzed, each conducted by a different tester, and different methods are used, and different methods are used [4].

“A recent literature review has confirmed that there are gender differences, but they are limited and are often influenced by various factors, such as age and function. emphasizes that their influence depends largely on their age and language.

Boys seem to have “weaker” or “slower” abilities to learn a language. Boys represent more than 70% of late speakers and only 30% of early speakers. Research

on the development of early language (the first three years of life) finds consistent differences between boys and girls in the process of developing early communication and language learning.

These differences are seen not only in the development of the language system, but also in the development of general social communication skills. In the development of many communication features, boys lag behind girls - eye contact, gesture use, gesture imitation, joint attention, social reference, and so on [4].

However, differences in language development can be the product of differences in the development of society as a whole. communication systems, early gender differences, and speaking skills have been studied in more detail.

In the early years of life, girls learn the language faster than the average boy and have vocabulary. For example, in 16 months, girls have 95 dictionaries and boys have 25 dictionaries. A similar pattern is confirmed in the acquisition, understanding and production of different languages, in lexical and grammatical development [3].

For example, boys produce girl combinations after an average of 3 months. The biggest differences between the sexes are at the developmental points when children develop new communication and language skills.

The pathologies of communication, speech, and language vary in etiology, prediction, and presentation. In clinical settings, it is important to first distinguish between communication, speech, and speech disorders.

Although these terms seem to be similar and interchangeable, communication skills (communication knowledge, verbal and non-verbal) are important for language acquisition (a system of symbolic symbols used for complex communication).

Dialogue refers to the language system engine (acoustic signal production) as the last “connection” of the development chain, and is one of the possible ways to express the language (the other is to write, sign, etc.).

One of the most interesting phenomena in the regulation of communication, language and speech disorders is the strong risk factor for the mentioned pathologies of the male genitalia and the protective factor for the female genitalia.

Speaking, language and communication skills vary greatly among the general population. Given the many areas of the brain and the complexity of cognitive and motor movements, how many years it takes to develop language or communication skills, and the important role that the environment plays in developing these skills, it is clear. that we are dealing with multi-faceted systems that take years to build.

Nonetheless, despite the enormous differences that exist regardless of gender; men and women, as a group, show consistent differences in communication and speaking skills.

Numerous epidemiological studies have found that boys have significantly higher levels of communication, language, and speech disorders than girls. Similarly, the process of developing normal communication and language skills is faster and more developed in girls than in boys.

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